

GLOBE Eclipse 2024: A Case Study of the Effects of the April 2024 Total Solar Eclipse on Cirrus Clouds and Contrails in the United States of America

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ABSTRACT

Solar eclipses are exciting events, attracting viewers globally. They are also a popular research topic, with scientists considering their effects on insolation, temperature, and even animal behavior. While some eclipse research focuses on how clouds change in the atmosphere, relatively few studies have considered how a solar eclipse may affect high-level clouds, including contrails. High-level clouds, such as cirrus and contrails, have a net warming effect on the Earth. High-level cloud coverage has been increasing, particularly in the midlatitudes, due to an increase in aircraft flights. There are many factors determining if contrails will form, including atmospheric conditions and aircraft engine. There is no shortage of research considering the various factors, but contrail forecasting remains difficult for meteorologists and aviators, perhaps especially during special phenomena that cause rapid atmospheric perturbations such as a solar eclipse. This research takes a unique perspective by coupling model data and satellite imagery with ground observations submitted by volunteers via The Global Learning and Observations to Benefit the Environment (GLOBE) Program during the 8 April 2024 total solar eclipse in six U.S. cities. Volunteer observations give us a clear timeline of the changes occurring before, during, and after the solar eclipse in multiple locations, allowing us to gather more detail than using models or automated ground stations alone. We use models to calculate hourly relative humidity with respect to ice (RHI) throughout the study period and compare contrail potential forecasts, while the volunteer observations tell us how cloud coverage was changing and the type of clouds, including contrails. Volunteers found cirrus and contrails typically increased near the local eclipse maximum (LEM), demonstrating that even temporally short events, like a solar eclipse, may affect atmospheric conditions enough to alter the likelihood of formation of these high-level clouds.

1. Introduction

1.1 Solar Radiation

Earth's atmosphere protects the surface by absorbing a portion of the incoming solar ultraviolet, visible, and infrared energy. Clouds and greenhouse gases are key components in how incoming and outgoing radiation are absorbed and scattered throughout the atmosphere ([NASA, n.d.](#)). The effects clouds have on radiation depend on their characteristics, e.g., high vs low altitude. High and thin clouds, such as cirrus, will predominantly transmit the incoming radiation and absorb the outgoing longwave radiation, emitting it back down to the surface ([NASA, 1999](#)). Because of this, high and thin clouds have a large greenhouse-forcing effect, meaning they have a net warming effect on the Earth.

1.2 Cirrus Clouds

From cloud observations, researchers have found that 20–30% of the globe is regularly covered by cirrus and other ice clouds, primarily near the tropics ([Liou, 1986](#); [Schröder et al., 2000](#); [Nazaryan et al. 2008](#)). Despite

their wide prevalence, cirrus clouds are not well studied, largely because of their high altitude in the atmosphere (typically above 6 km or 19,600 ft). Researchers have, however, discovered that cirrus clouds are made of nonspherical ice crystals, not water droplets like mid- and low-level clouds ([Liou, 1986](#)). Clouds that are made up of water droplets are conventionally treated as blackbodies, meaning they are assumed to absorb all incident radiation. With cirrus clouds being made of ice crystals, they do not behave as blackbodies; rather, they may reflect 47-59% of incident radiation and absorb 13-14% of upward solar flux and 27-40% of downward solar flux ([Reynolds et al., 1975](#)). Matusko ([2012](#)) discovered that cirrus clouds, despite their thin and wispy qualities, do contribute to scattered radiation in the atmosphere. In fact, global radiation intensity is greater in the presence of cirrus clouds than in clear sky conditions ([Vowinckel & Orvig, 1962](#); [Abakumova et al., 1989](#); [Anikin & Šukurov, 1989](#); [Matuszko, 2012](#); [Brasseur et al., 2016](#); [Singh et al., 2024](#)).

Several studies found supporting evidence that high cloud coverage is increasing, particularly between 30 and 65 degrees north latitude, due to an increase in aircraft flights ([Machta & Carpenter, 1971](#); [Changnon, 1981](#); [Liou, 1986](#)); the continental U.S. (CONUS) sits roughly between 25 and 49 degrees north latitude. If cirrus cloud coverage is increasing due to aircraft contrail formation, then there should be significant interest in further studying the relationship between contrails and the atmosphere, especially considering any radiative effects.

1.3 Contrails

Aligning with the research performed by Machta and Carpenter ([1971](#)) and Changnon ([1981](#)), we considered U.S. flight departure statistics beginning in 1960, just two years after jets were introduced as a new aircraft type for commercial flying (compared to the propeller planes). Jets have higher cruising altitudes and faster speeds than propeller planes, increasing the appeal and efficiency of flying. U.S. aircraft departures have continually increased each year since 1960, with the exception of 2020 due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

Different types of aircraft engines can affect the plane's likelihood of creating contrails. The most common commercial jet engine is the turbofan, used in aircraft such as the Boeing 737 and Airbus A320 ([NASA, 2021](#)). The turbofan engine has three different varieties: low-bypass, high-bypass, and afterburning. Most commercial jets have high-bypass turbofan engines, which likely have a higher occurrence of contrails than the other turbofan types ([Peters, 1993](#)).

Contrails can be formed in two different ways: directly and indirectly. Indirectly-formed contrails occur when the aircraft exhaust causes nucleation of ice crystals in the surrounding air, forming into a cirrus cloud that would not have formed without the aircraft's influence ([Jensen & Toon, 1997](#); [Demott et al., 1997](#); [Kärcher et al., 1998](#); [Lee et al., 2009](#); [Lee et al., 2021](#); [Brasseur et al., 2016](#); [Singh et al., 2024](#)). Directly-formed contrails originate directly from aircraft emissions when the surrounding air temperature is below 230 K (-43.15 °C) and the aircraft is flying around 250 mb (approximately 10.6 km or 35,000 ft) ([Schmidt, 1941](#); [Appleman, 1953](#); [Schumann et al., 1996](#)). In this case, the contrail becomes visible almost instantly following the aircraft. The

air's humidity determines if the contrail spreads or evaporates. If the surrounding air is dry, the contrail evaporates quickly, often in less than a minute ([Kärcher et al., 1996](#); [Singh et al., 2024](#)); if the air is supersaturated with respect to ice, the contrail will grow and possibly form into a cirrus cloud ([Schumann & Wendling, 1990](#); [Minnis et al., 1998](#); [Mannstein et al., 2010](#); [Bier et al., 2017](#); [Schumann & Heymsfield, 2017](#); [Gierens & Vázquez-Navarro, 2018](#); [Singh et al., 2024](#)). A contrail's behavior and lifespan are dependent on many factors, so a contrail, even just a few minutes old, is much less predictable than a newly formed contrail ([Singh et al., 2024](#)). As a contrail ages, its spreading results in a decrease in ice crystal concentration. At the same time, the ice crystal diameters increase ([Schröder et al., 2000](#)). This mimics the properties of a young, naturally-formed cirrus cloud. If a contrail continues spreading and growing, it may appear the same as a naturally formed cirrus cloud to a ground observer ([Schröder et al., 2000](#)). Understanding the atmospheric conditions that support the transformation of a contrail into a cirrus cloud is an important step in understanding how contrails may be affecting the atmosphere and radiative forcing. So far, researchers have identified relative humidity, updraft velocity, and ice crystal concentration and shape as some of the key components ([Schröder et al., 2000](#); [Duda et al. 2001](#); [Singh et al., 2024](#)); although Dzambo and Turner (2016) argue that ice cloud formation may not be correlated to higher relative humidity with respect to ice (RHI) values. All three of these components can be affected by solar radiation, whether directly or indirectly. Directly, solar radiation heats the atmosphere, which can cause updrafts ([NASA, 2021](#)). Previous research has also found an inverse relationship between solar radiation and relative humidity ([Tasie et al., 2018](#); [Kesavan & Senthilkumar, 2019](#); [Shrestha et al., 2019](#)). With ice crystal concentration, the relationship is more nuanced, as ice crystals can form in several ways. Ice crystal formation can be dependent on air and cloud temperature, but the ice crystal concentration depends on other variables, such as convection and cloud lifespan ([Mossop, 1985](#)), and soot particle emissions from the aircraft ([Burkhardt et al., 2018](#)). Ice crystal shape also varies with water vapor density and temperature until reaching ice saturation, where it achieves the equilibrium shape of a hexagonal plate ([Pruppacher & Klett, 1980](#)).

The unfortunate events around 9/11 led to various studies about contrails and their effects. With flights being grounded for several days after the attack and hence no contrail formation, researchers found the diurnal temperature range to be greater—i.e., the difference between the daytime and nighttime temperatures was larger than on days with typical air traffic and contrails ([Travis et al., 2004](#); [Kalkstein & Balling, 2004](#)). These studies further show contrails' net warming effect on the atmosphere, with cooler temperatures at night in the absence of contrails.

1.4 Solar Eclipse Effects

Outside the everyday Earth-Sun interactions, special phenomena can affect cloud and contrail formation. During a solar eclipse, the Moon blocks the Sun and casts a shadow on the Earth. This sudden blocking of the Sun affects the atmosphere, such as by causing temperature and solar radiation perturbations. These eclipse effects can result in further changes in the atmosphere, as previous research suggests the rapid change in

temperature during an eclipse generates atmospheric gravity waves ([Chimonas & Hines, 1970](#); [Butcher, 1973](#); [Hanuise et al., 1982](#); [Fritts & Luo, 1993](#); [Altadill et al., 2001](#); [Zerefos et al., 2007](#); [Chen et al., 2011](#)). (These atmospheric gravity waves fundamentally differ from the similarly named gravitational waves that are ripples in spacetime, per Einstein's theory of general relativity.) Atmospheric gravity waves, herein referred to simply as gravity waves, refer to how air moves vertically through the atmosphere. Some studies also attribute the gravity waves to the cooling of the ozone layer ([Zerefos et al., 2007](#); [Gerasopoulos et al., 2008](#)). Zerefos et al. ([2007](#)) also found that eclipse-initiated gravity waves can result in cloud formation, including cirrus cloud formation. Reviewing gravity waves and their effects is beyond the scope of this paper, but the related finding of cirrus formation during the solar eclipse is relevant to this research, as we consider changes in high-level clouds with respect to the 8 April 2024 total solar eclipse. Solar eclipses offer a rare snapshot of the Earth-Sun relationship and are often chosen as research topics to help provide insight into how the brief decrease in solar radiation may affect Earth's atmosphere and surface. Trees et al. ([2024](#)) found that cumulus clouds will begin dissipating at solar obscurations of approximately 15%. In a study of the 29 March 2006 total solar eclipse, part of which occurred over Greece, researchers observed an increase in cirrus clouds just after totality, affecting their measurements of direct solar irradiance ([Kazadzis et al. 2007](#)).

1.5 Ground Observation Contributions

Often, ground observations provide information on sky classifications, including those pertaining to cloud cover and cloud type. While some ground weather stations can report cloud type, most only report cloud coverage. To combat these issues, this research incorporates data from The Global Learning and Observations to Benefit the Environment (GLOBE) Program. The GLOBE Program is an international science and education program sponsored by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) and supported by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), the National Science Foundation (NSF), and the U.S. Department of State, that works to increase environmental awareness, increase scientific understanding of the Earth, and improve student achievement in science and mathematics. GLOBE also works with other organizations, such as the Civil Air Patrol (CAP). GLOBE provides a simple avenue for volunteers to submit their own observations to an open dataset via GLOBE Observer, the app of the GLOBE Program. This research is particularly interested in volunteer-submitted observations with cloud cover and cloud type, specifically those submitted during the total solar eclipse that occurred on 8 April 2024 ([Figure 1](#)). During phenomena such as eclipses, people will often relocate to the area where the phenomenon is happening. Moving weather station equipment can be costly, in both time and resources, as well as risk damage to the equipment. Ground stations also typically record measurements in set intervals, possibly missing changes that occur on small temporal scales, like an eclipse. This gives greater value to volunteer-submitted data, such as those through GLOBE. Data from volunteers may be viewed as inconsistent or untrained, but volunteers can provide unique datasets, as they can easily relocate and make observations throughout specific events that automated equipment may miss. Dodson et al. ([2019](#)) and Colón Robles et al. ([2020](#)) also argue the importance of volunteer data.

During the 8 April 2024 total solar eclipse, ground observers noticed an increase in cirrus clouds after totality, similar to Kazadzis et al. (2007), but 2024 observers specifically noticed changes in contrails. This research focuses on cirrus cloud and contrail changes reported by ground observers via GLOBE with respect to the progression of the solar eclipse. Using the ground observations and additional professional datasets, we closely examine several cities with a good spread of volunteer-submitted data. By studying several cities, within and outside the path of totality, this research seeks to determine if it is plausible that the solar eclipse may influence cirrus clouds and contrails and if further research would be beneficial.

Figure 1
Map of the total solar eclipse on 8 April 2024. Provided by NASA.

2. Data & Methods

2.1 GLOBE Observer Data

Volunteers submitted observations during the eclipse via the GLOBE Program's GLOBE Observer app. Observations were collected before, during, and after the eclipse throughout North America and other regions of the world. The GLOBE Observer app collects data from volunteers as described by Weaver et al. (2019), Dodson et al. (2019), and GLOBE Observer (2018). This research focuses on specific locations where the numbers of observations were robust, and the observations indicated skies were not completely overcast or obscured. Of the hundreds of locations represented by the GLOBE Observer data, several locations in CONUS stand out (Figure 2, Figure 3). While the path of totality was not sought to be the main study location, the majority of observations were made within this path, as it was more appealing to those traveling for the eclipse. Overall, GLOBE Observer collected more than 7,000 cloud observations from more than 2,100 people on the day of the eclipse.

As mentioned above, it can be difficult to distinguish between a natural cirrus cloud or a contrail that expanded into one. For this reason, and because of the potential radiative effects of cirrus clouds, this research considers reports of either, but excludes analysis of reports of cirrostratus and cirrocumulus. We recognize contrail reports are not only dependent on atmospheric conditions, but also the number of jets overhead. In an effort to combat varying flights throughout the study period over each given location, we also note the types of contrails that were reported: short-lived contrail (SLC), persistent spreading (PS), and persistent non-spreading (PNS). This research provides two case studies below, with several more locations noted for their reports of high-level cloud changes.

CONUS experienced the solar eclipse between 16:00 – 21:00 Coordinated Universal Time (UTC), with local eclipse maximum (LEM) mostly between 16:00 – 18:00 UTC, depending on location. This research is interested in examining approximately one hour before the local eclipse began to one hour after the local eclipse ended in each respective location. The GLOBE data were binned with the nearest big city (population \geq 50,000), provided the distance between each datum and a big city did not exceed 150 km (roughly a $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ difference over CONUS). We chose to group the data into the nearest big cities because of the availability of other data sources, i.e., weather stations at major airports. We then grouped the data by their relation to their local eclipse start, maximum, and end times in 15-minute intervals. This gave us a clear timeline of the reports of the atmospheric conditions before, during, and after the eclipse at each location while minimizing the effect of reports made during LEM, when the sky may be too dark for proper cloud identification. GLOBE also requested volunteers not to make observations during LEM, as the team wanted everyone to be able to enjoy the eclipse. The specific time range studied for each location is noted below in the results section.

Figure 2

A map of the solar eclipse path. The blue swath represents the path of totality, red lines represent the totality percentage in 20% increments, black dots are locations where volunteers submitted observations to GLOBE, and red points with a white center are cities chosen for this research.

Figure 3

Similar to Figure 2 but only showing the observation locations chosen for this research with their city labels.

2.2 Synoptic Meteorological Conditions

The eclipse path crossed over multiple regions of CONUS with varying meteorological conditions. On the day of the eclipse, 8 April 2024, the maximum and minimum temperatures within the path of totality ranged approximately 10 – 32 °C and -1 – 21 °C, respectively. The coolest temperatures occurred in Maine and the warmest in Texas. The majority of the path of totality did not experience temperatures colder than 10 °C. Surface weather maps provided by NOAA show high-pressure systems along the east coast and over the western and midwestern states. Cold fronts moved east from Illinois and Tennessee through Ohio and into the southeastern U.S. There was an occluded low-pressure system over southern Minnesota. The system continued moving over the Great Lakes region through 12:00 UTC on 9 April 2024. Southern states received up to 10 cm of rain overnight from 8 April to 9 April (Figure 4a,b). A 250 mb weather map indicates relatively uniform upper-level winds over the central and southeastern U.S., with a positively tilted trough over South Dakota, Wyoming, Nebraska, and Arizona (Figure 4c). This 250 mb wind map is nearly identical to the 200 and 300 mb maps, making it a good representation of jet stream activity. By 9 April 2024, the trough had moved slightly to the east to include New Mexico. On 8 April, a jet streak – an area of very strong winds in the jet stream – was off the Pacific coast of Mexico. The following day, a jet streak was over the Great Lakes, stretching from Iowa and southern Wisconsin to Pennsylvania and New Jersey. This jet streak and its strong winds on the day of the eclipse brought warmer and moister air from the southwest towards the path of the eclipse, increasing the likelihood of cloud formation.

Figure 4

Surface weather and 250 mb wind maps provided by NOAA. From left to right: (a) surface weather map, valid 12:00 UTC on 8 April 2024; (b) 24-hour precipitation valid 12:00 UTC on 8 April 2024 to 12:00 UTC on 9 April 2024; (c) 250 mb wind map valid 12:00 UTC on 8 April 2024.

2.3 Additional Datasets

We also considered several other datasets to provide further insight into the atmospheric conditions surrounding the eclipse. For each of the locations, we analyzed the nearby Automated Surface Observing System (ASOS) data, specifically the 5-minute ASOS data. While some ASOS sites can report cloud type, most only report cloud coverage, and they are typically most reliable for clouds at and below 12,500 ft (3,810 m). We also looked at Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellite (GOES) matches, weather reports,

contrail potential maps, and Goddard Earth Observing System Composition Forecasting (GEOS-CF) model replay data. The ASOS data were provided by each airport in the respective cities. GOES match reports are a feature provided by GLOBE that shows the volunteer what the overhead satellite detected with respect to low-, middle-, and high-level clouds. While the satellite does not report cloud type, it does report cloud cover percentage for each level (low, middle, and high) and the atmosphere overall. Coupling the satellite view with the volunteer data gives us both top-down and bottom-up views of the atmosphere.

The GEOS-CF model replay dataset provides hourly model data for 23 levels of the atmosphere between 1000 and 100 mb. Each level has several variables, including air temperature and relative humidity (RH), which are of particular interest here. Using the improved Magnus formula ([Alduchov & Eskridge, 1996](#)), we were able to calculate the hourly RH with respect to ice (RHI) from the given model data. RHI, as mentioned above, is important when considering the likelihood of contrail formation. When $RHI > 80\%$, conditions are typically favorable for contrail formation; $RHI > 100\%$ indicates the air is supersaturated with respect to ice, and there is a high probability a contrail will form and continue to grow. Air becomes supersaturated when it holds more moisture than the air's temperature supports. This occurs when the vapor pressure is greater than the saturation vapor pressure. Once the water vapor or ice crystals come in contact with a nucleus, such as an aerosol particle in the air, they can condense and form clouds.

Contrail formation is difficult to predict. There is no single model or prediction method that is widely accepted to accurately forecast contrail formation. This research considers several sources and models to provide the best prediction possible. Maps from Reviat show both jet flight paths and areas favorable for contrail formation over the U.S. during the solar eclipse ([Figure 5a – g](#)). According to the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) 2024 Air Traffic by the Numbers report, peak air traffic occurs 13:00 – 22:00 UTC; suggesting that there would not be any significant changes in air traffic during the study period ([FAA, 2024](#)). In addition, we do not consider the types of aircraft engines and their impact in this research. A contrail formation potential (CFP) ensemble, produced and provided by Dr. Dave Duda of the NASA Langley SatCORPS team, shows model agreement among eight different model runs that consider atmospheric conditions affecting CFP ([Figure 6a – c](#)). The CFP ensembles presented in the figure were updated three hours apart and derived from multiple runs of the North American Mesoscale (NAM) and Rapid Refresh (RAP) numerical weather forecast models. For each member of the three ensembles in [Figure 6](#), the NAM and RAP model temperatures, pressures, and relative humidity data were compared with the Schmidt-Appleman criterion for contrail formation ([Schmidt, 1941](#); [Appleman, 1953](#)) to determine which areas would support persistent contrail formation in the upper troposphere (any level between 150 and 400 mb). In addition, to eliminate regions where contrails may be obscured by thick cloudiness, dissipate, or disperse quickly due to atmospheric conditions, areas with model-forecasted thick cloudiness (composite radar reflectivity > -9 Dbz (RAP) or > -15 Dbz (NAM)), high vertical wind shear between 300 and 200 mb ($> 0.009 \text{ s}^{-1}$), or strong descending air motion at 300 mb (pressure vertical velocity $> 0.1 \text{ Pa s}^{-1}$) were excluded from each member forecast. Each CFP ensemble is composed of four NAM forecasts with forecast lead times ranging from 9 to 30 hours and four

RAP forecasts with lead times of 7 to 19 hours. By combining several forecasts, the most consistent areas of contrail formation were identified, and it is expected that regions with more model agreement will more likely form contrails (hence the description of model agreement in [Figure 6](#) as a confidence factor). [Figure 6](#) presents the ensemble model agreement for three forecast times during the eclipse. The GLOBE Observer reports thus offer an opportunity to test the reliability of the confidence factor to predict regions of persistent contrail formation.

Figure 5

Reviat maps valid on 8 April 2024 over CONUS. Copyright 2023 Breakthrough Energy, LLC.

The white patches represent areas with potential for contrail formation. White lines with arrows indicate a jet flight moving over the area. Blue lines represent contrails with a net cooling effect; orange represents contrails with a net warming effect. Top row, from left to right: (a) valid 16:00 UTC; (b) valid 17:00 UTC; (c) valid 18:00 UTC; (d) valid 19:00 UTC. Bottom row, from left to right: (e) valid 20:00 UTC; (f) valid 21:00 UTC; (g) valid 22:00 UTC.

Figure 6

CFP map showing the level of agreement among eight models, valid 8 April 2024 at various times. Blank areas indicate models do not expect atmospheric conditions to be favorable for contrail formation. Green areas, such as those in the Pacific Ocean off California’s coast and over the western coast of Mexico, represent agreement among 1-2 models. Areas with orange, such as over the Florida Peninsula and north-central Texas continuing east through Ohio demonstrate that all eight models agreed there were favorable conditions for contrail formation. The black dots represent the center solar eclipse path, with the time of when the solar eclipse will reach its maximum in each location. Top row, from left to right: (a) valid 15:00 UTC; (b) valid 18:00 UTC. Bottom row: (c) valid 21:00 UTC.

3. Results

3.1 Case Study #1: Toledo, Ohio

Toledo was in the path of totality, attracting observers. Toledo experienced the solar eclipse from approximately 17:56 – 20:27 UTC and was in totality 19:12 – 19:14; we chose to look at data collected between 17:00 – 22:00. [Figure 7](#) shows the distribution of volunteer observations, where the majority were made +/- 30 minutes of the LEM. The fewest observations were collected between 21:00 – 22:00, which is expected as eclipse observers return home. [Figure 8](#) displays the distributions of the percentage of volunteer observations that reported cirrus clouds and various types of contrails. An increase in occurrence in both PS and PNS, as well as cirrus reports, could indicate an increase in atmospheric supersaturation with respect to ice, particularly when paired with a decrease in SLC. The timing of these events, relative to the solar eclipse, could mean a correlation between the solar eclipse, supersaturation, cloud coverage, and contrail formation.

Figure 7

Graph showing the distribution of observations submitted through GLOBE Observer. The peak occurred at 18:45 UTC, where 22 observations were submitted. The number of observations per timer interval decreases after the LEM. Observations remained lower through the end of the eclipse and after.

Figure 8

Graph showing the distribution of the percent of observations submitted through GLOBE Observer that contained cirrus clouds (blue line) and contrails (orange line), with black bars representing standard error of proportion. Both decreased before the LEM and increased after the LEM.

3.1.1 Overall Cloud Coverage

Using the qualitative reports from volunteers in conjunction with the quantitative reports from GOES, high-level clouds were found to be the main contributor to overall cloud coverage throughout the study period (Table 1-6). Volunteers and GOES reported the overall cloud coverage to typically be broken, with a slight decrease in cloudiness after the LEM. Figure 9a – c displays images provided by the GLOBE volunteers, representing the sky conditions they saw. The ASOS site reported clear skies for the entire solar eclipse duration, indicating its limitations in capturing high-level clouds over a widespread area (Table 1). Weather reports from that day indicated fair skies, stating that the clouds were mostly thin cirrus clouds that would not obstruct the view of the eclipse.

Figure 9

Photos submitted by the same volunteer in Toledo, OH during the eclipse. From left to right: (a) photo submitted 17:19 UTC, with visible contrails; (b) photo submitted 19:10 UTC, with visible contrails; (c) photo submitted 20:19 UTC, there is a noticeable decrease in cloud coverage compared to the previous images.

3.1.2 Cirrus Clouds and Contrails

During the first hour of the study period, 17:00 – 18:00, half of the volunteer observations reported cirrus clouds, and 82% reported contrails, with the majority being persistent, specifically PS. Throughout the hour, the percentage of reports with cirrus declined while those with contrails increased. The eclipse had just begun around 18:00, so these reports are independent of any potential eclipse-related effects. Once the eclipse began, the percentage of reports with cirrus clouds continuously decreased until just after the LEM, where the percentage increased from about 14% to almost 45% just 30 minutes after the LEM. The reports with cirrus clouds continued increasing, despite the overall cloud coverage decreasing, and remained at 100% once the eclipse concluded. There were many fewer observations after the eclipse compared to before and during, so the post-eclipse observations are not as robust and may not represent the area as well.

The percentage of reports with contrails follows a similar pattern to that of cirrus clouds. There is a steady decrease in percentage throughout the beginning of the eclipse until right before the LEM. Here, the reporting percentage increases and reaches 100% before the eclipse ends and remains at 100% through the end of the study period. Again, it is noted the number of observations decreased after the eclipse, possibly affecting the results. When considering the type and average number of contrails reported per observation, PS and PNS were dominant. Both saw increases in number of reports within 15 minutes of the LEM, then tapered off to pre-eclipse numbers as the eclipse ended. The total average number of contrails reported per observation also began increasing near the LEM and continued to increase until about 30 minutes post-LEM, when the average number of contrails steadied and the number of observations decreased. The average number of SLC per observation was higher before the eclipse started than during it, with noticeable decreases about 15 minutes into the eclipse. This contrasts the average number of PS and PNS per observation, both of which first decreased at the start of the eclipse, but near the LEM, they increased to averages higher than pre-eclipse.

We used the GEOS-CF model replay data to look at the atmospheric conditions that determine contrail formation. The RHI continuously increased throughout the duration of the eclipse; however, the sharpest increase occurred near the LEM, when the RHI increased from 147.8% during the previous hour to 153.7% ([Figure 13a](#)). The continuous supersaturation of the atmosphere indicates favorable conditions for contrail formation, especially those that will persist and grow, as we noted above. Using the CFP maps, the models do not indicate favorable conditions at 15:00 UTC, before the local eclipse started ([Figure 6a](#)). Three hours later, all the models agree there were favorable conditions ([Figure 6b](#)). Finally, at 21:00 UTC, most models still indicate favorable conditions ([Figure 6c](#)). The increase in favorable conditions as the eclipse began likely indicates the conditions continued to be favorable during the eclipse leading up to the LEM. With these models, the data are updated every three hours, so it is difficult to completely understand what they may have shown closer to the LEM, at 19:00, but it appears safe to assume the models were all in agreement that the conditions were favorable for contrail formation. Comparing these maps to those provided by Reviat, we can see continuous flights over Toledo throughout the study period, likely indicating a significant change in the number of flights having minimal effect on the observed number of contrails ([Figure 5a – g](#)).

3.2 Case Study #2: Dallas, Texas

Like Toledo, Dallas was also in the path of totality, experiencing the solar eclipse from approximately 17:23 – 20:02 UTC. Totality, or LEM, occurred 18:40 – 18:44; we chose to look at data collected between 16:00 – 21:00 UTC – an hour earlier than the Toledo data, given that Dallas experienced the eclipse earlier. [Figure 10](#) displays the distribution of volunteer observations. There were just about an equal number of observations made 17:00 – 18:00 as 18:00 – 19:00, with these time intervals accounting for almost one-third of the observations made in Dallas. As expected, the number of observations decreased as the eclipse ended. [Figure 11](#) displays the distributions of the percentage of volunteer observations that reported cirrus clouds and various types of contrails.

Figure 10

Graph showing the distribution of observations submitted through GLOBE Observer. The peak occurred at 18:30 UTC, where 33 observations were submitted. The number of observations per time interval decreases after the LEM. Observations remained lower through the end of the eclipse and after.

Figure 11

Graph showing the distribution of the percent of observations submitted through GLOBE Observer that contained cirrus clouds (blue line) and contrails (orange line), with black bars representing standard error of proportion. Both increased before the LEM and decreased after the LEM.

3.2.1 Overall Cloud Coverage

Dallas began the day with severe weather warnings, with threats of tornadoes and large hail. These threats caused some solar eclipse viewing events to be canceled, possibly deterring people in the area from witnessing the event. Thankfully, the severe weather held off during the eclipse, and the city was able to view the astronomical event and make observations throughout. Generally, Dallas saw clouds at all levels (low, middle, and high) during the eclipse. Volunteers reported clearing skies, from overcast to broken and scattered, with a mix of cloud types leading up to the eclipse. This continued through the LEM, after which observations indicate cloud coverage decreased to scattered and isolated. Near the end of the eclipse and post-eclipse, volunteers observed more broken skies again. GOES imagery aligned with the volunteer observations, seeing the same decrease in cloud coverage as LEM approached and an increase surrounding the end of the eclipse; however, GOES and volunteer observations differ in the high-level cloud coverage reported. GOES reported no high-level cloud coverage, while volunteers did report cirrus, contrails, and other high-level clouds ([Table 2](#)). This likely indicates that most clouds during the eclipse were mid- and low-level clouds, but since the sky was not overcast, it still allowed volunteers to see through to any high-level clouds. It may also be difficult for satellite algorithms to differentiate between cloud levels when the majority of clouds are lower in the atmosphere. [Figure 12a – c](#) shows some images of the sky submitted by the volunteers. The ASOS site reported a similar pattern in cloud coverage as the volunteers but with a greater decrease in cloud coverage leading up to the LEM ([Table 2](#)). Again, there was a noticeable drop in temperature at the LEM.

Figure 12

Photos by different volunteers in Dallas, TX during the eclipse. From left to right: (a) photo submitted 16:46 UTC, Note the prevalence of low clouds and lack of contrails and cirrus clouds; (b) photo submitted 18:14. There are more high-level clouds present than in the previous image; (c) photo submitted 19:45 UTC. The skies continued clearing and now very few clouds are visible.

3.2.2 Cirrus Clouds and Contrails

In the first hour, only 7.5% of volunteer observations reported cirrus clouds, but this percentage increased until reaching its maximum value of 22% at 18:00. It dipped slightly in the following 15-min interval then rose again around the LEM. The reports remained relatively steady until closer to the end of the eclipse, where the percentage of reports with cirrus clouds decreased. Likewise, the percentage of reports with contrails reached its maximum between 18:00 – 19:00, near the LEM. Despite an increase in cirrus clouds and contrails, the

decrease in overall cloud coverage during this period indicates the decrease likely occurred in mid- and low-level clouds. After the LEM, the percentage of reports with cirrus clouds decreased, reaching zero after the eclipse ended.

As stated above, the percentage of reports with contrails was highest near the LEM. The majority of contrails reported throughout the study period at Dallas were SLC; however, notably, 60% of all observed PNS contrails and 50% of all observed PS contrails were reported between 18:00 – 19:00, near the LEM. The patterns of these contrail reports follow those of the cirrus reports – increases observed near the LEM, then decreases through to the end of the eclipse. The total average number of contrails reported per observation increased as the eclipse began and was greatest after the LEM, before decreasing at the end of the eclipse. So, while reports with contrails were decreasing after the LEM, the number of contrails per report was increasing.

Using the GEOS-CF model replay data, RHI was above 100% for the whole study period ([Figure 13b](#)). It increased as the eclipse started but then decreased right after the LEM from 152.6% to 145.2%. This decrease does correlate with the decreases we saw in the percentage of observations with contrails but does not explain the increase in the number of contrails per observation. Looking at the Reviatie jet flight path map ([Figure 5a – g](#)), Dallas appears to have had a continuous flow of jet flights during the eclipse; however, the contrail formation maps do not have strong agreement that there were favorable conditions. At 15:00, there was no model agreement on favorable conditions for contrails existing over Dallas, although some models show Dallas close to the contrail potential region ([Figure 6a](#)). By 18:00, three of the eight models found favorable conditions over Dallas ([Figure 6b](#)). Another three hours later half of the models agree ([Figure 6c](#)). The lack of straightforward agreement among the models indicates the difficulty in determining the atmospheric conditions over Dallas during the study period. The presence of contrails over the area may have been more dependent on the conditions within the jet engine since the models did not agree on whether atmospheric conditions were favorable. This lack of agreement further indicates the importance of observations taken from the ground since they can confirm whether contrails were present and if they spread or formed into cirrus clouds.

3.3 Other Notable Locations

Several other locations reported changes in cirrus clouds and contrails throughout the eclipse, but they were not as extensively examined as the above case studies for various reasons, such as too few data points or gaps in data collection times. These locations are included to demonstrate further that eclipse viewers observed and reported changes in cirrus clouds and contrails.

3.3.1 Boston, Massachusetts

Study period: 17:00 – 22:00 UTC; LEM: 19:29

Volunteers in Boston observed an increased presence of both cirrus clouds and overall contrails once the eclipse began through to the LEM. Specifically, both PS and PNS contrails increased in reports while SLC

decreased. The percentage of observations that reported cirrus, as well as those that reported contrails, decreased for 30 minutes post-LEM, after which they both increased again. The increase in the percentage of reports with cirrus clouds came slightly after that of the contrails, possibly indicating older contrails were growing into cirrus clouds as new contrails formed. The 30-minute window after the LEM where both the percentage of reports with cirrus and contrails decreased may indicate a change in atmospheric conditions that made it temporarily unlikely for cirrus and contrails to form and persist. There were no satellite matches over Boston after 19:00 UTC, which was before the LEM; however, leading up to 19:00, GOES did see an increase in high-level clouds during the same time period as the volunteers ([Table 3](#)). The CFP maps do not indicate Boston to have favorable atmospheric conditions for forming contrails at 15:00, before the eclipse began ([Figure 6a](#)). By 18:00, conditions became more favorable, and some models agreed that contrails could form ([Figure 6b](#)). Again, the models are only updated every three hours, so they did not capture atmospheric conditions near the LEM, which occurred between 19:00 – 20:00 for the eastern U.S. All eight models were in agreement in the third model run at 21:00 that the atmospheric conditions over Boston were favorable for contrail formation ([Figure 6c](#)). These maps show the conditions for contrail formation increased between 15:00 – 21:00. Yet, volunteers noted decreases in both cirrus and contrail presence, suggesting the atmospheric changes that made contrail formation more likely did not coincide with when data were submitted by volunteers.

3.3.2 Erie, PA

Study period: 17:00 – 22:00 UTC; Totality/LEM: 19:16 – 19:20

Most observations reported increases in cirrus clouds throughout the study period, with the largest percentage of observations reporting cirrus near the LEM. This increase coincided with an increase in the percentage of observations that saw contrails. Most commonly, volunteers reported PS contrails, with PNS also increasing near the LEM. The satellite imagery was in agreement with the volunteer observations of high-level clouds, seeing an increase in the high-level clouds beginning just before the LEM and continuing through after the eclipse ended ([Table 4](#)). Observed contrails decreased slightly near the end of the eclipse. Before the eclipse, the contrail formation maps do not indicate favorable atmospheric conditions over Erie ([Figure 6a](#)). By 18:00 the CFP maps show Erie near areas with strong model agreement on favorable conditions; and 21:00 has strong model agreement (>6 models) that conditions are favorable ([Figure 6b – c](#)). Given the timing of cirrus and contrail observations from the volunteers, it seems possible that the improvement in favorable conditions contributed to the increase in both near the LEM, and further increased the likelihood of the contrails growing into cirrus clouds.

3.3.3 Suffolk, Virginia

Study period: 17:00 – 22:00 UTC; LEM: 19:19

Once the eclipse began, the percentage of cirrus reports increased from 0% to 100%; reports with contrails also increased. Volunteers noted an increase in all three types of contrails leading up to the LEM; afterward, they observed mostly PS and PNS. The percentage of reports with cirrus clouds remained at 100% until after the eclipse ended, as did the percentage of reports with contrails, indicating the continued presence of cirrus and contrails. GOES saw similar high-level cloud changes as the volunteers, reporting a cloud coverage increase near the LEM, which then remained steady through the end (Table 5). While the presence of cirrus persisted throughout the eclipse, the decrease in observations of SLC and increase in PS and PNS could point towards conditions becoming more favorable for persistent contrails during the eclipse. The CFP models did not show favorable conditions prior to the 21:00 run, at which time more than half of the models were in agreement (Figure 6a – c). The increase in observed contrails and cirrus clouds likely coincided with the atmospheric conditions becoming more favorable.

3.3.4 Washington, D.C.

Study period: 17:00 – 22:00 UTC; LEM: 19:20

Volunteers reported increases in both cirrus and all three types of contrails leading up to the LEM. Cirrus cloud reports continued to increase as the eclipse ended, while contrail reports gradually decreased, with reports of SLC decreasing first, then PS and PNS following. Similar to Suffolk, the satellite saw high-level cloud coverage increasing beginning near the LEM and not decreasing until after the eclipse ended (Table 6). Again, the models did not display favorable conditions until 21:00, when all of them agreed (Figure 6a – c). The delayed decrease in PS and PNS contrails, in relation to SLC, may indicate persistent contrails grew into cirrus as atmospheric conditions became more favorable, while SLC began to persist and grow. More extensive research and data points would be needed to determine any relation.

The tables below show Cloud coverage as reported by GOES and ASOS. GOES overall cloud coverage and specific high cloud coverage are included for each study location. Initialisms are as follows: ovc = overcast, brk = broken, sct = scattered, iso = isolated, few = few, and clr = clear. Dashes represent missing data. Table 1 - Toledo, Ohio; Table 2 - Dallas, Texas; Table 3 - Boston, Massachusetts; Table 4 - Erie, Pennsylvania; Table 5 - Suffolk, Virginia; Table 6 - Washington, D.C.

Toledo, OH	GOES Overall Cloud Coverage	GOES High Cloud Coverage	ASOS Overall Cloud Coverage
Time (UTC)			
17:00	brk	brk	clr

17:30	ovc	brk	clr
18:00	ovc	ovc	clr
18:30	ovc	ovc	clr
19:00	ovc	ovc	clr
19:30	ovc	brk	clr
20:00	brk	sct	clr
20:30	brk	brk	clr
21:00	brk	sct	clr
21:30	sct	few	clr
22:00	brk	sct	clr

Dallas, TX Time (UTC)	GOES Overall Cloud Coverage	GOES High Cloud Coverage	ASOS Overall Cloud Coverage
16:00	brk	few	ovc
16:30	ovc	none	brk
17:00	iso	none	sct
17:30	brk	none	brk
18:00	iso	none	sct
18:30	none	none	clr
19:00	none	none	clr
19:30	iso	few	brk

20:00	brk	none	few
20:30	brk	none	sct
21:00	brk	none	brk

Table 3			
Boston, MA	GOES Overall Cloud Coverage	GOES High Cloud Coverage	ASOS Overall Cloud Coverage
Time (UTC)			
17:00	sct	iso	clr
17:30	sct	iso	clr
18:00	sct	iso	brk
18:30	brk	sct	brk
19:00	ovc	brk	brk
19:30	-	-	brk
20:00	-	-	clr
20:30	-	-	clr
21:00	-	-	clr
21:30	-	-	-
22:00	-	-	clr

Table 4			
Erie, PA	GOES Overall Cloud Coverage	GOES High Cloud Coverage	ASOS Overall Cloud Coverage
Time (UTC)			
17:00	ovc	-	brk

17:30	ovc	none	sct
18:00	brk	none	few
18:30	brk	few	brk
19:00	brk	sct	ovc
19:30	ovc	none	brk
20:00	ovc	brk	clr
20:30	ovc	brk	clr
21:00	ovc	brk	clr
21:30	ovc	brk	clr
22:00	brk	brk	clr

Suffolk, VA	GOES Overall Cloud Coverage	GOES High Cloud Coverage	ASOS Overall Cloud Coverage
Time (UTC)			
17:00	none	none	clr
17:30	none	none	clr
18:00	none	none	clr
18:30	few	none	clr
19:00	none	none	clr
19:30	few	few	clr
20:00	-	-	clr
20:30	brk	sct	clr

21:00	sct	few	clr
21:30	sct	iso	clr
22:00	iso	few	clr

Washington, D.C. Time (UTC)	GOES Overall Cloud Coverage	GOES High Cloud Coverage	ASOS Overall Cloud Coverage
17:00	iso	none	clr
17:30	few	none	clr
18:00	sct	none	clr
18:30	sct	none	clr
19:00	few	few	clr
19:30	-	-	few
20:00	ovc	ovc	brk
20:30	ovc	brk	few
21:00	ovc	brk	few
21:30	-	-	clr
22:00	-	-	clr

4. Discussion

[Table 7](#) displays the changes volunteers saw in each of the respective cities. Toledo, Dallas, and Erie were in the path of totality; Boston, Suffolk, and Washington, D.C. were not. Volunteers in five of the six cities reported observing increases in contrails as the LEM approached, often with each reaching its maximum percentage of observations near the LEM. Toledo was the only city where observations indicated a decrease in cirrus and contrails before the LEM. It was most common to see changes in contrails match the changes in

cirrus clouds, i.e., if cirrus cloud presence decreased, contrail presence did, too. Observing a decrease in cirrus clouds would likely coincide with a decrease in contrail formation because they require similar atmospheric conditions to form. Contrail formation is dependent on more variables, like jet engine efficiency and temperature, so a decrease in contrail observations may not indicate decreased cirrus presence. Likewise, contrail observations may decrease as the contrails form into cirrus clouds.

This research sought to find out whether the total solar eclipse on 8 April 2024 may have affected cirrus clouds and contrail formation, both of which can have net warming effects on the Earth’s environment. This research presents specific case studies using data submitted to GLOBE by volunteers before, during, and after the eclipse. Using data from ground observations allowed us to compare ground views of cloud changes to those detected by satellites and predicted by models. The volunteer data provided us with snapshots throughout the eclipse which gave us more detail than if we used satellite or model data alone. Comparisons of the volunteer data and satellite imagery show they agreed on cloud coverage changes, encouraging us that the volunteers submitted accurate observation reports. While no definitive conclusions can be made from these results, it does seem possible that the gradual blocking of the Sun by the Moon made atmospheric conditions more favorable for cirrus clouds and contrails to form.

[Table 7](#) displays the changes in the percentage of reports with cirrus clouds and contrails provided for each study location. The changes are separated into two time periods: before and after the LEM. Cities highlighted in **bold** were within the path of totality. Except for Toledo, all cities had an overall increase in the percentage of reports with cirrus clouds and contrails before the LEM. After the LEM, the results were more mixed; two cities had a decrease in cirrus cloud report percentage, and three had a decrease in contrail report percentage.

	Leading up to LEM		After LEM	
	Cirrus Clouds	Contrails	Cirrus Clouds	Contrails
Toledo, OH	Decreased	Decreased	Increased	Increased
Dallas, TX	Increased	Increased	Decreased	Decreased
Boston, MA	Increased	Increased	Decreased immediately after, then increased	Decreased immediately after, then increased
Erie, PA	Increased	Increased	Increased	Decreased
Suffolk, VA	Increased to 100% of reports	Increased to 100% of reports	Remained at 100% of reports	Remained at 100% of reports

Washington, D.C.	Increased	Increased	Increased	Decreased
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4.1 Cirrus and Contrails

Rather than being instantaneous, changes in cirrus and contrail presence likely lagged behind changes in the atmospheric conditions. This may explain the gradual increases in cirrus and contrails pre-LEM. In the case of Toledo, there was almost a 1.7 °C increase in temperature at 18:00 at the 250 mb level, according to the GEOS-CF model replay data (Figure 13a – f). While it’s possible this increase affected the likelihood of high-level cloud formation, the temperature remained below the -38 °C threshold for cirrus formation. What’s more likely is the cirrus clouds thickened as the temperature increased and transformed into cirrostratus or even possibly a mid-level cloud (Funk, n.d.). More analysis of Toledo’s atmospheric conditions would be required to explain the observed decrease in cirrus further.

There were no qualitative differences between cities within the path of totality and those outside it with respect to changes in cirrus clouds and overall contrails. The only notable difference is the type of contrails that were reported. In Boston, volunteers reported SLC occurrence decreased, despite overall contrail report increasing before the LEM. Similarly, Suffolk and D.C. volunteers observed that SLCs decreased after the LEM. D.C. also saw decreases in PS and PNS contrails, but they persisted longer than the SLCs. The cities in the path of totality did not have notable changes in the type of contrails; however, overall, SLCs were not as present as PS and PNS contrails in all six locations. Decreases in SLCs that coincide with increased PS and PNS contrails likely indicate the atmospheric conditions became more favorable for contrails to grow and spread. In locations where an increase in cirrus reports followed increased contrail reports, it is possible the contrails grew into the cirrus clouds.

4.2 Eclipse-Induced Atmospheric Perturbations

Previous studies of eclipse-induced meteorological perturbations have generally focused on the lower troposphere and the ozone layer, where solar heating is particularly large compared with the rest of the atmosphere. Subsequently, the effect of eclipses on the upper troposphere and related cloud species has received relatively little focus. Nevertheless, this issue has been addressed. For example, using sounding rockets, Subrahmanyam et al. (2011) studied two eclipses occurring over India during 2009 and 2010. They found two distinct responses of the upper troposphere and the lower stratosphere to a solar eclipse. The first was a rapid cooling effect of ~2-3 °C occurring during the onset of the eclipse, which appeared to be radiatively driven. The second was a delayed warming response of up to 8 °C occurring several hours after the eclipse, with a related decrease in the cold point tropopause height of 1.7 km. Manoj et al. (2021) also found the tropopause height and mean planetary boundary layer decreased during the 2019 annular solar eclipse. The secondary warming appears to be dynamically driven, as the atmosphere contracts in response to the large radiatively-driven cooling signal during the eclipse. This compression may result in strong downdrafts, especially in the stratosphere (Das et al., 2023). Unlike radiation, which travels practically instantly relative to

the timespan of a solar eclipse, the dynamical perturbation requires minutes to hours to propagate vertically and horizontally through the lower atmosphere, and as a result, the dynamically-driven warming signal is offset from the time of the eclipse. Subrahmanyam et al. (2011) reported the main warming signal being above the tropopause, which might affect contrails in the lower stratosphere but likely would not affect cirrus in the upper troposphere.

If the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere responded to the 2024 eclipse in a similar manner to the aforementioned eclipses, then these temperature perturbations are potentially significant enough to affect high-level cloud cover during and after the eclipse. Many regions affected by the 2024 eclipse had cirrus cover and contrails before the start of the eclipse, indicating that at least some layers of the upper troposphere were near saturation. A cooling of 2-3 °C in a near-saturated upper tropospheric layer would be favorable for cirrus and contrail formation. Furthermore, regions with cirrus coverage prior to the eclipse may have further enhanced cooling at the cloud level, as upper tropospheric absorption of insolation is increased within cirrus clouds (Reynolds et al., 1975; Vowinckel & Orvig, 1962; Abakumova et al., 1989; Anikin & Šukurov, 1989; Matuszko, 2012; Brasseur et al., 2016; Singh et al., 2024). On the other hand, the subsidence and dynamical warming after the eclipse could potentially cause cirrus and contrails to dissipate, while also suppressing cirrus and contrail formation. While this may be a mechanism to explain observed decreases in cirrus and contrails in general, it would be difficult to explain why this would affect clouds during the eclipse.

4.3 Upper-Air Composition

High-level clouds, such as the cirrus and contrails presented in this research, are made of ice crystals rather than water droplets. These ice crystals are most likely to form when the air is supersaturated with respect to ice. We found each location's respective hourly RHI by calculating saturation vapor pressure with respect to ice using the Improved Magnus formula and GEOS-CF replay data. It is important to note that the GEOS dataset has limitations, such as only being available hourly and potentially not capturing the true and full eclipse effects. Saturation vapor pressure is solely dependent on air temperature. Except for Dallas, all study locations remained below -50 °C at 250 mb. Dallas' 250 mb temperature remained between -40 and -50 °C. While the air may have been supersaturated, other factors affect cloud formation, including aerosols (Maciel et al., 2023), vertical wind (Peters, 1993; Kärcher et al., 2023), and gravity waves (Zerefos et al., 2007; Kärcher et al., 2023). Maciel et al. (2023) found a strong positive correlation between ice crystal concentration and large aerosol (>500 nm) concentrations. This research does not consider aerosols' effect, but future research may want to consider them, particularly in cases comparing big cities with more rural areas.

The likelihood of cirrus and contrail formation increases when upward motion is present in the atmosphere (Peters, 1993; Kärcher et al., 2023). While Zerefos et al. (2007) found the eclipse can initiate gravity waves, Kärcher et al. (2023) report that these gravity waves can result in mesoscale temperature fluctuations (MTFs). These MTFs, in turn, cause vertical winds (Kärcher et al., 2023). In Figure 4c, the winds to the east of the trough are stronger than to the west, indicating divergence. This divergence causes downward motion, which,

according to Peters’ (1993) and Kärcher et al.’s (2023) research, would decrease the potential of cirrus and contrail formation. Using the same figure, the winds begin converging over the southeastern CONUS off the Atlantic coast, causing upward motion and increasing the potential. This may help explain why Suffolk, VA, and Washington, D.C., were the only two cities not to have a decrease in the percentage of volunteer reports of cirrus and contrails at any point during the study period.

Figure 13

RHI and air temperature at 250 mb for each study location, calculated using the GEOS-CF replay model data. RHI > 100% indicates supersaturation, meaning an increased likelihood of contrail formation. Orange columns represent RHI; blue line represents air temperature (°C); vertical black line represents when the LEM occurred. Top row, from left to right: (a) Toledo, OH; (b) Dallas, TX; (c) Boston, MA. Bottom row, from left to right: (d) Erie, PA; (e) Suffolk, VA; (f) Washington, D.C.

4.4 Future Work

Future work would include studying more phenomena, such as partial solar eclipses, as well as days without special events for cloud formation comparison purposes. Perhaps more specialized research could test various jet engines to observe the extent to which contrail formation is dependent on the jet itself when atmospheric conditions are similar. Including reports of cirrostratus and cirrocumulus clouds may also be beneficial, as some sources state that, although rarer, contrails can form into those cloud types (Met Office, n.d.). Aerosol composition should also be considered, as their effect on cirrus cloud formation is not well quantified (Maciel et al., 2023). The importance of continuing to study and understand these net-positive greenhouse-forcing clouds is evident as discussions centering around Earth’s current and future climate increase. While no immediate actions are recommended as a result of this research, future research may suggest ways to reduce contrail formation or reduce the lifespan of contrails.

5. Acronym & Initialism Glossary

ASOS – Automated Surface Observing System

BRK – Broken (Clouds)

CAP – Civil Air Patrol

CFP – Contrail Formation Potential

CLR – Clear (Clouds)

CONUS – Continental United States of America

FAA – Federal Aviation Administration

GEOS-CF – Goddard Earth Observing System Composition Forecasting

GLOBE – Global Learning and Observations to Benefit the Environment

GOES – Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellite

ISO – Isolated (Clouds)

LEM – Local Eclipse Maximum

MTF – Mesoscale Temperature Fluctuations

NAM – North American Mesoscale

NASA – National Aeronautics and Space Administration

NOAA – National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration

NSF – National Science Foundation

OVC – Overcast (Clouds)

PNS – Persistent Non-Spreading

PS – Persistent Spreading

RAP – Rapid Refresh

RH – Relative Humidity

RHI – Relative Humidity with respect to Ice

SCT – Scattered (Clouds)

SLC – Short-Lived Contrail

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